

Data Analyst

Jim Blair (he/him)

"I love having a job where I constantly get to solve puzzles and learn about new subjects from the experts."

Bio

After getting a bachelor's degree in physics, Jim joined the research analytics department at a nearby academic health center. During his 3 years as a data analyst, Jim has worked primarily on querying the enterprise data warehouse to find data for clinical researchers.

Generating his queries with SQL code, he compiles the retrieved data into reports. He also pulls information for RPPRs and is beginning to build databases for clinical studies. Jim works on 5 or 6 different projects during any given week and must be ever mindful of permissions and approvals for sensitive data, as well as time spent on projects for billing purposes. Jim enjoys his work and believes it is a vital first piece of the research puzzle.

Starting with understandable, clean, and accurate data is the crux of reproducible science, allowing for complex statistical and mathematical analyses later in the research process. Jim has grown his skills in 'interviewing' researchers to determine exactly what data they are seeking. He has also become knowledgeable about where to search for various types of data and when to stop (i.e., the point of diminishing returns).

Education: BS, Physics

Years of experience: 3

Work location: Working remotely is the norm but face-to-face time with colleagues and the research team is a priority

Goals

- Find opportunities to collaborate with biostatisticians, to support collaborative work
- Obtain credit for his work through publication
- Advocate for and embrace open science practices

Software attitude & use

- Jim embraces the opportunity to learn new technologies and wants to build his skills in Python
- His colleagues are his greatest resource, helping with SQL code, report and form building, and encouraging him to experiment with new technologies
- Shares code on GitHub
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace; JIRA
- Collaboration: Box, Zoom, Slack
- Specialized resources: frequently used coding and data tools include SQL and SQL server, R, Tableau, Git; other key resources include REDCap, the EDW, Epic, PowerChart, tools to track clinical studies and their budgets, Smartsheet

Outputs

- Co-author on researchers' publications for the study-related databases he built
- Conference presentations and posters
- Documentation on analysis procedures for his department
- Extensive work on GitHub

Pain Points

- Regularly needs to reconstruct data from messy sources
- Slow response times from researchers is frustrating

Motivators

- Move beyond data searches and become experienced in more complex analyses
- Approach problems from many angles. When an analysis isn't working, Jim finds another approach and strives to figure out what he can do better
- Maximize reproducibility in methods and analyses

Wants/Needs

- More time in the day to complete data searches and analyses
- To continue building his skills in a suite of analysis programs
- Wishes original data sources were cleaner
- Greater institutional focus on data management
- A quicker way to know the best communication style to use with each researcher
- Better ways to share information within his department about effective PI communication

Professional Development

During collaborations, Jim learns about clinical methods and subject matter from researchers, while he instructs them in analytical methods and technical jargon

Wants to take a statistics class to understand what biostatisticians do with the data that analysts have collected, which can inform form-building

Self-paced learning through online tutorials such as LinkedIn Learning

Queries Stack Overflow and user forums